

PANDEM-Source, a tool to collect or generate surveillance indicators for pandemic management: A use case with COVID-19 data

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Abstract

Introduction

PANDEM-Source (PS) is a tool to collect and integrate openly available public health related data from heterogeneous data sources to support infectious diseases surveillance for pandemic management. The tool may be used also for pandemic preparedness by collecting or generating surveillance data for training purposes. It was developed as part of the EU funded Horizon 2020 PANDEM-2 project during the COVID-19 pandemic as result of a close collaboration in a consortium of nineteen partners including six European public health agencies, one hospital, and three first responders organisations.

Methods

A requirement gathering process with EU pandemic managers in the consortium was performed with the objective of identifying and prioritising a list of variables and indicators useful for surveillance and pandemic management. Using COVID-19 pandemic as a use case, we developed PS, a tool to map, collect, and integrate data used for surveillance from different data sources with the purpose of feeding all necessary data to be displayed in the PANDEM-2 dashboard.

Results

PS routinely monitors, collects, and standardises data from from open or restricted heterogeneous data sources (users can upload their own data). It supports traditional surveillance indicators and health resources reported by national and international agencies, and non-traditional surveillance indicators such as those captured in social and mass media, participatory surveillance and sero-prevalence studies. The tool can also calculate indicators and be used to produce data for training purposes by generating synthetic data from a minimal set of indicators to simulate pandemic

scenarios. PS is currently set up for COVID-19 surveillance at European level but can be adapted to other diseases or threats and regions.

Conclusion

PS design provides flexibility to collect heterogeneous data from open data sources or to upload end users' own data and customise surveillance indicators. These features are supplemented by the ability to generate realistic epidemiological synthetic datasets that can be used for training purposes. All these features make PS a unique and valuable tool for pandemic management.

With the lessons learnt during the COVID-19 pandemic, it is important to keep building capacity to monitor potential threats and develop tools that can facilitate training all the necessary aspects to manage future pandemics. The open source availability of PS¹ and the supporting documentation to facilitate easy adaptation to future threats or different training scenarios may represent a cost efficient impact tool for pandemic management.

1 Introduction

PANDEM-2 is an Horizon 2020 EU-funded project aiming to develop and demonstrate innovative solutions to strengthen pandemic preparedness and response at EU Level for public health emergencies at subnational, national, EU and global level. The IT tools are accessible through an interactive decision support dashboard that encompasses data from a variety of domains including traditional epidemiological surveillance, non-pharmaceutical interventions, contact tracing, and hospital resources, but also non-traditional surveillance data such as social or mass media analysis and participatory surveillance data and flights. An integrated epidemiological and hospital resource capacity modelling is also available to support planning and what-if scenarios.

The PANDEM-2 consortium includes partners that cover key aspects of pandemic preparedness and response including six National Public Health Agencies in the EU (RKI in Germany, FOHM in Sweden, THL in Finland, INSA in Portugal, NIPH in Romania and RIVM in the Netherlands), first responders organisations (Austrian Red Cross, Italian Red Cross, INEM Portugal and the Radboud Medical Centre, the Netherlands). All the tools developed were designed and validated in close collaboration with the consortium partners and are distributed using open source licences.

PANDEM-Source (PS) is an IT surveillance tool to collect and integrate openly available public health related data from heterogeneous data sources to better support communicable disease surveillance for pandemic preparedness and response. PS main objective is to identify, map and integrate pandemic-related data from multiple sources into a coherent pandemic-management database so it can provide all the necessary data to feed the PANDEM-2 dashboard with, when available, near real time data. Its data model was developed in close coordination with the consortium partners aiming to address the challenge of monitoring the COVID-19 pandemic response, but it is flexible and can be adapted to other diseases or new threats, variables and indicators by changing source description files without changes in code.

Effective training of public health professionals is an essential element of pandemic management [1] which is targeted by the PANDEM-2 project by developing training scenarios and simulation

¹ <https://github.com/pandem2/pandem-source>

exercises [2]. During the simulation exercises the PANDEM-2 dashboard displays realistic information matching a specific designed scenario for training.

Collecting and producing the required data can be a challenge due to the broad scope of information available on the dashboard for pandemic management. To ensure quality and facilitate processes PS includes monitoring systems/visualisation of data collection by source and features to detect missing data on an initial set of indicators to create a realistic full synthetic dataset covering all necessary variables to perform simulation exercises. These features were used during the PANDEM-2 simulation exercise which focused on assessing PANDEM-2 tools on Public Health Emergency Operation Centres in Germany and the Netherlands during an influenza pandemic scenario. The initial set of indicators were produced using the PANDEM-2 modelling tools and included confirmed cases, deaths, and vaccination status by age group for Germany and the Netherlands. Subsequently, PS generated data for the remaining variables in the dashboard for all EU/EEA countries, including subnational level and distribution by age group, gender, and comorbidities. These variables included population level data on contact tracing, hospital resources and social media analysis trends (sentiment, emotion and suggestion). After data generation, PS performed the calculations for those indicators that need to be computed such as hospital occupancy, incidence rates, mortality rates, vaccination coverage, etc.

In this paper we will describe PS features and design with the aim of disseminating its characteristics and capabilities to strengthen pandemic preparedness and response.

2 Methods

2.1 Identification of relevant variables and indicators for pandemic management

The PANDEM-2 project commenced twelve months after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in the EU. The initial work involved a requirement gathering process with the European public health agencies and first responders on the PANDEM-2 consortium. We conducted a structured process to identify the most important variables and indicators to be included into a dashboard that aimed to be useful to cover current and future needs in pandemic management. The process started with a web and literature search and meetings with experts which allowed us to identify relevant data sources for the project as well as which ones were open access. . In parallel, all consortium participants were invited to provide a list of data requirements according to their ideal dashboard to be used for pandemic management. The list of requirements and meeting outputs were analysed to produce an initial list of categorised variables [2]. A data survey was distributed to end users to score the importance and to provide details on data priorities and availability for all the identified variables focusing on COVID-19 use case. These outputs were used to accomplish a final refinement list of variables taking in consideration PANDEM-2 partners assessment on importance, priorities and data availability. We defined an automatic data collection process for variables available in open data sources and data generation for non available variables. We generated synthetic data for missing relevant variables to showcase the full potential of the PANDEM-2 dashboard and to introduce it as a training resource for pandemic management. The resulting dataset is described in [3]. The figure 1 schematises this approach by stating tasks, outputs and dependencies.

Figure 1: Process followed for defining pandemic management variables and indicators to be collect or generate

2.2 Design goals

PS was designed to achieve the following design goals.

- Adding new sources and variables should be possible without changes in code.
- Keep a track of the reporting institution and methodology applied.
- Capability of integrating data from a wide variety of sources and formats.
- Automatic data standardisation based the source description having capacity from transcoding from multiple coding schemas e.g. the region name in local languages to the region code.
- Integration, type or standardisation errors are informed to the data manager.
- The data integration process should be fault tolerant. Errors after data submissions should not lead to data loss.

2.3 Assumptions

In order to generate a generic approach for data integration we defined the following assumptions:

- A variable is a label indicating general concept and some variables are computed indicators that are expected to be collected directly from different data sources e.g. number of cases, incidence rate, symptom name, etc. Names are previously defined and are associated with a particular definition, the type (numeric, text), coding schema and/or calculation method.
- Limited variables types: integer, numeric, date, datetime, string.
- Variables can be grouped in observations and attributes. Observations contain mainly epidemiological information like “number of cases” or “incidence rate”. Attributes provide extra information or characteristic details associated with a particular observation e.g., the age group of the observed cases.
- Variables can be tied together in as tuples containing an unique measure, a date, a source, and several attributes:
 - Confirmed cases:13
 - Pathogen: dengue
 - Age group: 10-18
 - Date: 2021-12-13
 - Geo: Brussels
 - Source: COVID-19 ecdc-dataset.

- Time series are built using observation values in time for tuples with the same attributes e.g. the evolution of confirmed cases for a given age group and city . Indicators can be calculated using functions at the time series level. e.g. the time series for `rt_number[]` is obtained based on the time series of the number of confirmed cases over time for a disease and the given population on that geographical location.
- For a given set of attributes and an observation there can be only a single unique value.
- Data sources provide stable identifiers that can be used for unequivocally retrieving the associated data.
- Data source resources can be read in a tabular format.

2.4 Data pipeline design

To tackle the issue of data collection and generation we developed the data labelling schema (DLS), a declarative methodology based on text files, for documenting, standardising and integrating surveillance data sources and producing homogeneous and comparable time series. This methodology provides a common approach to address the heterogeneity of formats, sources and types of data found during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The DLS integration pipeline uses a set of source description files providing information including ownership, how to detect changes to trigger an import, the files format, how to read the files in a tabular format, how to map columns to PS variables and the applicability of data generation. The list of PS variables contains functions for calculated indicators such as incidence or mortality rate so they can be automatically calculated when necessary parameters are present. Such functions are defined in R language, a widely used language in the domain of epidemiology. Advanced calculations can be performed by integrating external algorithms. For instance, social media analysis data is obtained thanks to natural language processing algorithms developed by the University of Galway. A final step is performed of aggregation up to country level if not already provided by the source.

Synthetic data generation was addressed by defining data generation formulas on the list of variables. PS will automatically detect which variables are missing when integrating data and will evaluate the synthetic formulas to generate them. When partitioned data was missing e.g. deaths by comorbidity, a weighted distribution function was applied. When base data was missing e.g. number of people traced for contact tracing, we created hypothetical estimations based on the number of confirmed cases. Data generated in such a way is tagged in the resulting dataset as ‘synthetic’. The resulting data is stored as json files and available using a REST API [4] allowing to query the integration process and obtain the results. The figure 2 shows the entire PS integration pipeline.

Figure 2: **PANDEM-Source (PS) integration pipeline**

3 Results

3.1 The list of variables

The process of defining pandemic management variables produced a list of 126 observations and indicators which we present here grouped into 29 main variables. Variables are also grouped into families associated with different aspects of pandemic management. Main variable variation are indicators calculated as rates of another variable or stratification by attributes. This structure is presented in table 1.

Data family	Main variable	Variations
cases	confirmed cases	by variant, by gender, by comorbidity, rate in population (incidence)
	number of notifications	rate in population
	active cases	rate in population
	recovered cases	rate in population
	rt number	

deaths	deaths infected	by bed type (ICU, ward), rate in population, rate in hospitalised, alert
	excess mortality	
hospital capacity	hospitalised infected	by bed type, by comorbidity, by comorbidity and bed type, rate in capacity, rate in population, rate in comorbidities, alert
	average length of stay	by bed type
	admissions	by bed type, by comorbidity, rate in capacity, rate in population
	available staff	by staff type, rate in population
	beds capacity	by bed type, rate in population
syndromic surveillance	primary care cases	by ILI vs SARI
	primary care positivity rate	by ILI vs SARI
testing and lab	performed tests	by variant, by test type, rate in cases (positivity), rate in population
	sequenced samples	by mutation, by variant, rate in population
vaccination	doses injected	by dose number, rate in population (vaccination coverage)
	people fully vaccinated	rate in population (vaccination coverage)
contact tracing	contact tracing cases	by being already a contact, by reached status, by reach in a day
	contact tracing contacts	by being already a contact, by reached status, by reach in a day
participatory surveillance	participants declaring symptoms	alert
	number of participants	
	estimated incidence	with confidence interval

	number of visits	by visit type
non pharmaceutical interventions	implemented_measure	by measure type (e.g. mask wearing) and measure group (e.g. contact tracing, testing, etc)
population studies	seroprevalence	by study name, by study type
	studied population	by study name, by study type
transport	Number of incoming flights	by country of origin
social and mass media	article count	by topic, sentiment, emotion and suggestion
referential	population	by population type

Table 1 list of PANDEM-Source (PS) variables

3.2 Integrated sources

PS uses a set of source description JSON files containing necessary information for integrating data and calculating time series. During the PANDEM-2 project we developed source description files for European Union countries using data from the COVID-19 pandemic. It is important to highlight that PS follows an all-hazard approach [5] and COVID-19 is only a use case that can be easily extended to support other diseases or threats, with their variables and indicators, as well as other geographical scopes.

Sources used to build the PANDEM-2 COVID-19 dataset [3] can be grouped on those used for indicators and those for standardisation. The list of sources implemented are the following:

- Sources used for Indicators
 - ECDC COVID-19 datasets [6]: Selection of datasets describing the EU members surveillance and response to the pandemic published by the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC).
 - COVID-19-Datahub [7]: A unified dataset collecting global fine-grained case data on the pandemic surveillance and response. This dataset is used for indicators that are not available at subnational level on ECDC datasets.
 - Our World in Data [8]: Our world in data is a scientific online publication that focuses on global problems. It provides several COVID-19 related datasets. This source was used to obtain extracted excess mortality data since this indicator was missing from previous sources...
 - Influenzanet [9]: a Europe-wide network to monitor the activity of influenza-like-illness (ILI) with the aid of volunteers via the Internet. It is operational in twelve countries. Influenza.net publishes datasets on participants declaring

- COVID-19 symptoms and healthcare seeking behaviour as well as provide estimated incidence for the participating countries.
- Twitter, via the Panacea Lab COVID-19 tweet collection [10]: A large-scale COVID-19 Twitter dataset for open science starting in march 2020. This dataset contains COVID-19 related tweet IDs. We obtained the list of IDS from the data sharing platform Zenodo.org[] and downloaded the tweet texts using the Twitter API. The tweets were annotated using Natural Language Processing models to produce dedicated time series by country.
 - MediSys [11]: The Medical Information System MedISys is an internet monitoring and analysis system developed at the JRC in collaboration with EC Directorate General SANCO to rapidly identify potential threats to public health using information from the internet. MedISys continuously monitors about 900 specialist medical sites plus all the generic EMM news, i.e. over 20000 RSS feeds and HTML pages sites from 7000 generic news portals and 20 commercial news wires in altogether 70 languages. We generated a connector for Medisys capable of extracting the last 30 days of articles for predefined topics but due to the lack of historic data collection this source could not be included on the COVID-19 dataset.
 - OpenSky Network [12]: OpenSky Network is a non-profit association that provides open access of flight tracking control data. It was set up as a research project by several universities and government entities with the goal to improve the security, reliability and efficiency of the airspace. The used dataset is a derived version from the full dataset published on Zenodo covering the period from 2019 to 2022.
 - Eurostat [13]: Eurostats is the statistical office of the European Union and publishes a wide range of datasets & statistics concerning European countries. We obtained information about available beds and hospital staff.
 - OECD [14]: The OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development). The OECD regularly publishes comparable statistics on numerous subjects. In the case of COVID-19 it was the selected source for getting an estimation on the evolution of the number of Intensive Care Unit (ICU) operational beds by country.
 - SeroTracker [15]: SeroTracker is a dashboard and data platform for SARS-CoV-2 serosurveys. They conduct an ongoing systematic review to track serosurveys (antibody testing-based surveillance efforts) around the world. Seroprevalence studies results were integrated.
 - Sources used for standardisation
 - Eurostat: [16] The NUTS classification (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics) is a hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU and the UK. Standard region codes and names were obtained.
 - Geonames.org [17]: GeoNames is a geographical database distributed under the creative commons attribution licence. It contains over 27 million geographical names. We used this source to extract ISO2 and ISO3 code equivalences and to obtain multilingual aliases for countries in the world and and regions in Europe.
 - ICD-10-CM [18]: The ICD-10 Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM) is a modification of the ICD-10 (International classification of diseases) used as a source for diagnosis codes in the United States of America. This source is used to get the list of pathogens.
 - ISCO-08 [19]: ISCO-08 ISCO-08 is a four-level hierarchically structured classification that allows all jobs in the world to be classified into 436 unit groups. We used this codification to store information about resource types in hospitals such as doctors or nurses.

- Our airports [20]: OurAirports is a free site where visitors can explore the world's airports, read other people's comments, and leave their own. This site provides freely available files with the list of world airports.

3.3 PANDEM-Source (PS) pipeline implementation

3.3.1 Source description

The Data Labelling Schema (DLS) is a declarative approach that requires a detailed description of the sources using JSON files in complement with a list of variables, mappings and indicator formulas. Based on the source description, PS takes care of all transformations to perform the data acquisition, validation, standardisation, and, if necessary, the calculation indicators or data generation. Each data unit goes through a standardised integration pipeline (Figure 2) which reduces risk of errors and ensures updated metadata is kept of the whole database. Each variable is linked to a unit, a source, a date of integration and and mapped to a target “pre-defined” PS variable providing a description, a referential (if transcoded was necessary) and associated formulas. If new variables need to be added, the list of variables can be directly modified to include new concepts without changes in code. A CSV file can be easily modified by a data manager allowing complete autonomy on variable definitions which is a key feature to allow adaptation to unknown or novel threats. The file is publicly available on

<https://github.com/pandem2/pandem-source/blob/main/pandemsource/data/list-of-variables.csv>

3.3.2 Data Acquisition

The source descriptor file of each source must also define all necessary information to monitor each source, trigger automatic updates when changes are performed and how to interpret file format to acquire data. Multiple acquisition channels were implemented including git repositories, URL and predefined Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). If a new channel is required, the user can provide custom R or python scripts to perform the data acquisition. PS checks for updates on a regular predefined basis using when available versioning methods to avoid downloading data to detect changes.

The source descriptor files also define the format of target files, including Excel, CSV, JSON and XML. Each format has its own formatting properties to interpret the provided data. If the source is too complicated or needs to be cleaned before integration, PS supports the usage of dedicated Python scripts to pre-process datasets.

3.3.3 Standardisation

A number of well-defined standards [21, 22] are included in PS and the tool automatically monitors and updates these references from public data sources to compute specific indicators, from NUTS, ISO country codes, ICD-10 diseases, or geonames. When input data does not match the expected format or referential data, PS provides a list of integration issues allowing the data manager to visualise and fix them. For instance, a source provides the number of confirmed cases for an unknown country, the data is ignored and details of integration issues are reported. The user can

define mappings using json files to support transcoding between different codification systems such as ISO3 or region names to NUTS.

3.3.4 Calculated metrics and indicators

Calculated indicators such as incidence rates, effective reproduction number (R_t) are produced by R scripts included in PS that can be also modified by any user with basic knowledge of R language. PS proceeds automatically to indicator calculation whenever all available parameters are provided by a source or already provided by a related source. Computing indicators instead of directly collecting it from different data sources ensures that the same methodology is used, thus supporting comparability. Aggregation from subnational to national level is also performed automatically.

3.3.5 Data generation

In the list of variable definitions, PS also includes formulas for data generation allowing creating the entire PS datasets with a minimal set of input variables. This data generation feature was designed to generate training datasets that can be used during simulation exercises. This feature was used during the PANDEM-2 simulation exercise, where an Influenza pandemic scenario initiated in two European countries using the PANDEM-2 dashboard was simulated. The PANDEM-2 modelling tools [23] were used to produce the time series for the number of cases, deaths hospitalisations and vaccinations and PS used its data generation functions for generating plausible data about social media posts, participatory surveillance, contact tracing, public health staff variations, syndromic surveillance and stratification by comorbidities age groups. This feature reduced the amount of effort needed for preparing the data for the simulation exercise.

3.4 PANDEM-Source (PS) architecture

PS is a python package that implements the DLS with out of the box definitions for integrating a wide range of indicators from heterogeneous surveillance data sources. It has been published on Pypi <https://pypi.org/project/pandem-source/> and its code is open under the EUPL² licence and it is available on GitHub <https://github.com/pandem2/pandem-source>.

PS has been implemented following a micro services architecture using the Actor Model and using the package with pykka³. Each actor receives messages, processes them one by one and can send messages to other actors. Messages can be any python object. This programming pattern allows to achieve a good level of parallelization of tasks while keeping a simple programming model and file access. For external algorithm integration we have used docker containers and REST APIs. The following classes of actors have been defined:

- **Orchestrator:** Launch actors, manage docker encapsulation, close actors
- **Storage:** Keep persistent information of the integration process and process all data storage operations.
- **Acquisition:** Triggers data integration of known data source files

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/european-union-public-licence_en

³ <https://pykka.org/en/latest/>

- **Data pipeline:** Ensures that integration is performed and ensures that the process will run until an end (error, warning, success)
- **Algorithms:** Execute a particular algorithm during the pipeline
- **Format readers:** Transform input files into dataframes
- **Dataframe reader:** Transform data frames into a list of non-standard tuples
- **Standardisation:** Transform a list of non-standard tuples into a list of standard tuples.
- **API:** Provides a REST API for accessing public endpoints
- **Variables:** Reads and writes standardised variable values. Provides a necessary mapping information to standardisation actor in order to standardise variable values e.g., Country Name => Code ISO

Figure 3: PANDEM-Source (PS) actor dependencies

3.5 Integrating social media analysis components

The integration of social media components necessary to classify tweets required the execution of Social Media Analysis (SMA) components developed as part of PANDEM-2. These components were packaged and exposed as an API and utilised a TensorFlow Serving Docker to facilitate its integration. PS includes all necessary parameters to automatically launch the right docker tensor flow

server locally if not already running on the configured URL, the only information that is needed is the folder where the models are saved. The models are launched using configuration files, so adding new models does not require changes on its code.

Once the models are running, PS will evaluate any source including the variable article text and add the resulting model outputs as new attributes of the related tuple.

After annotation the article text is removed, and PS will calculate the aggregations for each used algorithm and produce the related time series.

3.6 Integrating the Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) Simulator

Another external algorithm utilised is the Multiparametric Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) simulator [24]. This tool used to generate realistic time series by variant and mutation not being publicly available. The simulator can combine data from real data sources such as cases by variants, and number of hospitalisations by age group and vaccination status. The resulting datasets are built using machine learning approaches to find a realistic combination of these variables. This simulator is written in R.

PS uses the simulator which needs to be installed as an R package. It uses git to locally check if there have been changes on the input files before launching the simulator.

3.7 PANDEM-Source (PS) python package

PS includes a Shiny⁴ app for validating the integration and to visualise the integrated time series. The integration dashboard is structured as follows:

3.7.1 Data integration page

List of integrated sources showing current integration status, next expected check for changes, the history of data sets collection executed, and issues found see Figure 5. This page refreshes automatically.

⁴ <https://shiny.rstudio.com/>

Show 50 entries

	Name	Progress	Step	Status
1	COVID-19 Datahub	95.56%	ended	success
2	ECDC Atlas	100.00%	ended	success
3	ECDC COVID-19	81.67%	ended	success
4	ECDC COVID-19 Simulated	70.00%	precalculate_started	in progre
5	Eurostats NUTS	100.00%	ended	success
6	GeoNames	70.00%	precalculate_started	in progre
7	ICD-10-CM	100.00%	ended	success
8	Influenza net	100.00%	ended	success
9	MediSys	100.00%	ended	success
10	OpenSky-Network-CovidDataset	100.00%	ended	success
11	OurAirports	70.00%	precalculate_started	in progre
12	RIVM COVID-19 manual	100.00%	ended	success
13	SeroTracker	100.00%	ended	success
14	THL COVID-19 manual	100.00%	ended	success
15	Twitter	100.00%	ended	success

Showing 1 to 15 of 15 entries

Show 50 entries

	Id	Source	Progress	Step	Status
1	5	serotracker	100.00%	ended	success

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

Show 200 entries

Id	Job Id	Source	Table	Severity	Issue Type	Step	Line Number	File
246	5	SeroTracker	serotracker	warning	ref-not-found	standardize_started	1	5/in/5_git_serotracker_sars-+data_serotracker_dataset.cs
247	5	SeroTracker	serotracker	warning	ref-not-found	standardize_started	1	5/in/5_git_serotracker_sars-+data_serotracker_dataset.cs
248	5	SeroTracker	serotracker	warning	ref-not-found	standardize_started	2	5/in/5_git_serotracker_sars-+data_serotracker_dataset.cs
249	5	SeroTracker	serotracker	warning	ref-not-found	standardize started	2	5/in/5_git_serotracker_sars-+

Figure 4 The PANDEM-Source (PS) data integration page

3.7.2 Available sources page

List of defined data sources including information about the source descriptor files such as acquisition channel and variable mappings see Figure 5.

Navigation: PANDEM II: Data Surveillance | Integration progress | **Data sources** | Data dictionary | Time series | About

Data Sources

Source

ECDC COVID-19 - ecdc-covid19-vaccination

Source definition

Source	ECDC COVID-19 - ecdc-covid19-vaccination
Description	Information about the volume of COVID-19 sequencing, the number and percentage of variants of concern by week, country and variant. Data collected by the ECDC from the GISAID EpiCoV database and TESSy
Tags	ECDC COVID-19
Reference User	TESSy (ECDC)
Reference Email	surveillance@ecdc.europa.eu
Data Quality	Official
Frequency	daily

Acquisition

Channel	url
Channel info	<ul style="list-style-type: none">url: https://opendata.ecdc.europa.eu/covid19/vaccine_tracker/csv/data.csv
Format	csv
Format info	<ul style="list-style-type: none">decimal_sign: .thousands_separator:date_format: isoweekencoding: UTF-8
Data Scope	
Globals	<ul style="list-style-type: none">source: NApathogen_name: COVID-19

Figure 5 The PANDEM-Source (PS) data source page

3.7.3 Data dictionary page

The entire list of variables defined on PS including all metadata and formula definitions, see Figure 6.

Family	Type	Variable	Base Variable	Definition	Unit	Partition
12_population_study	indicator	article count alert		Alert triggered by the number of articles going over the expected using a modified version of the ears algorithm	qty	<ul style="list-style-type: none">sourcetopicgeo_code
03_patient	indicator	icu patients alert		Alert triggered by the number of icu patients going over the expected using a modified version of the ears algorithm	qty	<ul style="list-style-type: none">sourcecase_statusgeo_code
02_deaths	indicator	deaths infected alert		Alert triggered by the number of infected deaths going over the expected using a modified version of the ears algorithm	qty	<ul style="list-style-type: none">sourcecase_statusgeo_code

Figure 6 The PANDEM-Source (PS) variable list

3.7.4 Time series page

Displays all the integrated time series. A dynamic filter system and the count of matching time series helps the user to explore and understand the underlying data see Figure 7. Time series from different sources can be easily compared.

Figure 7 The PANDEM-Source (PS) time series exploration report

3.7.5 Exporting data

Data processed by PS is available via a REST API. Which can be regularly called to get the most current data.

The REST API is also the way of acquiring data for the Shiny⁵ Integration Dashboard, so any functionality on the integration dashboard can be replicated on the PANDEM-2 database. Figure 8 displays the implemented endpoints of the REST API.

⁵ <https://shiny.rstudio.com/>

Figure 8 The PANDEM-Source (PS) time series exploration report

4 Conclusions

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and within the umbrella of PANDEM-2 project, PS has been developed with the advice of a large variety of health and public health experts to include relevant indicators for infectious disease surveillance and to monitor the health response that feeds the PANDEM-2 dashboard. During the PANDEM-2 simulation exercises, PS and PANDEM-2 dashboard have proven useful to facilitate training for pandemic management. The design provides flexibility to collect data from open data sources or to upload end users own data and customise indicators. PS can support public health agencies and first responders in developing their own data collection tools according to their specific training and response needs and reduce the development effort of building them from scratch. This flexibility and easy to customise feature is supplemented by the capacity to generate realistic epidemiological synthetic datasets that can be used for training purposes. All these features make PS a unique and valuable tool for pandemic management. To our knowledge, although some data collection tools have been developed during the COVID-19

pandemic [7, 25, 26], PS is unique in terms of flexibility and customisation to be adapted to different data sources or diseases or to develop new training. It also differs from by its broader approach, the heterogeneity of the data sources and collected data and its flexibility allowing it to quickly adapt to emergent threats imposing new data needs. We believe that these characteristics make the tool useful not only for training purposes but also, with further development and adaptation according to the context, to be deployed to support monitoring and managing an emergent epidemic or pandemic.

At the end of integration, PS also allows users to visualise the uploaded data as time series by time and geographical level or other shared attributes such as variant, or age group which may facilitate monitoring and validate the surveillance results before being captured in the dashboard (or just to visualise some results from some variables not incorporated in the dashboard). This approach also leverages visualisation and comparison of any kind of indicator independent of their nature. For instance, it allows visualisation of social media emotion trends together with the number of cases of a particular mutation or the evolution of the seroprevalence in a specific population or the evolution of people's opinions to specific public health related topics based on social media analysis.

PS is a ready to use open-source tool allowing pandemic managers to collect and harmonise multiple surveillance data on specific pathogens from traditional and non-traditional publicly available or restricted data sources. It currently includes a wide list of COVID-19 sources to collect data from different domains (cases, deaths, ICU occupancy, social media analysis, Lab and NGS data, non-pharmaceutical interventions) from different data sources such as ECDC or other public health agencies websites - via the COVID-19 Datahub scripts, Influenzanet, Twitter, MediSYS, etc.

In summary, PS contribute to the pandemic management community through:

- Out of the box data collection for pandemic preparedness and response.
 - Flexibility and customisation on data collection
 - Data can be visualised in the tool
 - Exploited directly through the PS API
 - Visualised through the PANDEM-2 dashboard
- Simplifies cross domain data collection for epidemiological surveillance
- Foundations for a multi-source multi threat early warning system
- Proposes a standard methodology for collecting surveillance data and computing indicators that could support standardisation and data sharing among countries.
- Data generation for training purposes.

It is relevant to highlight some potential limitations when using the tool: First, the data availability is a limitation factor. It is possible, as may happen at the beginning of an epidemic or pandemic, that data is still scarce. Second, we can find that, although some data may be potentially available from the health provision services, there are data sharing limitations in different scenarios; to share data with the general public or with other countries but also it may happen that there are restrictions to

share personal data for public health surveillance purposes without patient consent. Related with first and second, it is worth mentioning that often the most useful data to respond to at local level is not available or if available is sensitive due to data protection issues (possibility to identify individuals). Third, the list of data sources required (open or restricted) may substantially change over time but also for different threats or pathogens so the current data sources included in PS may need to substantially change according to the epidemiological need. Four, some users may need some training to install and use the tool (not always possible to have assistance). Despite these limitations, we believe that the fact of PS is a flexible and easy to customise tool that will facilitate its use and will represent a useful tool for preparedness and response related activities. IT solutions to facilitate and strengthen disease prevention and control are needed and will be developed in the coming years and PS , as well as other tools developed under the PANDEM-2 project, can be useful prototypes to be further developed according to future needs and threats.

5 Conflict of Interest

No conflicts of interests

6 Author Contributions

Francisco Orchard: Manuscript writing, software design and implementation. Co-coordination of PANDEM-2 surveillance workpackage.

Charline Clain: Software implementation and manuscript review

William Madie: Software implementation and manuscript review

Etienne Sevin: IT team leader, software design and manuscript review

Máire A. Connolly: Project Scientific Coordinator, manuscript review

Jessica Hayes: Project manager, manuscript review

Alexis Sentís: Epidemiological support, co-coordination of PANDEM-2 surveillance workpackage, and manuscript review

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9 Supplementary Material

No supplementary material provided

10 Data Availability Statement

The data generated with the tools is subject to a different publication.

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